

Stochastic Tables: Methodology for Assessment and Development of Elementary Mental Computational Skills

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1. Introduction

To determine and improve the level of elementary mental computational skills, I utilize "stochastic tables": <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20546444> containing 64 uniform operations each. These operations cover fundamental arithmetic: addition and subtraction (within 20), as well as multiplication and division (within 100). These tables are termed "stochastic" because the sequences of operands are randomly generated, simulating the spontaneous emergence of these operations in everyday mathematical tasks. Stochastic tables were first applied during the 1984 experiment: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20613599>. The statistical processing of the results was conducted in 1993 and validated in 2026 using several AI-driven conversational models: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20600368>."

2. Methodology and Procedure

- **Implementation:** Pupils complete the tables in written form, both in class and at home.
- **Measurement:** The total time from the start to the completion of the table must be recorded.
- **Training:** Before the initial diagnostic test, a training session is required to ensure pupils understand the format and are accustomed to performing a large series of elementary operations.
- **Precision:** For class-wide testing, results are typically rounded to the nearest five seconds (in the pupil's favor) to facilitate management when multiple pupils finish simultaneously.

3. Assessment Criteria

Evaluation is based on two criteria: **Total Running Time** and **Number of Errors**.

- *Note:* The permissible limits calculated for these stochastic tables represent "surplus approximations," meaning they are sufficiently mild demands for a student to meet.

4. Normative Values (Limit Thresholds)

The following tables provide limit values based on the time elapsed since the mastery of the multiplication table ("Period"). The limit values were calculated for the standard tables including 64 similar elementary operations. The first position is running time in minutes and seconds: "6:27" – 6 minutes 27 seconds. The second position is number of errors.

1. ADDITION

Period	< 0.5		0.5-1		1-2		2-3		3-4		> 4	
Excellent	6:27	0	6:09	0	5:00	0	4:17	0	3:59	0	3:52	0
Good	7:53	2	7:30	2	6:09	1	5:22	1	5:00	1	4:47	1
Limit	11:02	4	10:30	4	8:41	3	7:44	3	7:12	3	6:51	2

2. SUBTRACTION

Period	< 0.5		0.5-1		1-2		2-3		3-4		> 4	
Excellent	6:32	0	6:09	0	5:03	0	4:25	0	4:07	0	3:59	0
Good	8:07	2	7:40	2	6:16	2	5:34	1	5:12	1	5:00	1
Limit	11:35	4	10:59	4	8:57	4	8:06	3	7:34	3	7:12	3

3. MULTIPLICATION

Period	< 0.5		0.5-1		1-2		2-3		3-4		> 4	
Excellent	6:05	0	5:37	0	4:12	0	3:44	0	3:36	0	3:33	0
Good	7:14	1	6:42	1	5:07	1	4:35	1	4:23	1	4:16	1
Limit	9:46	3	9:04	3	7:11	3	6:29	3	6:07	2	5:51	2

4. DIVISION

Period	< 0.5		0.5-1		1-2		2-3		3-4		> 4	
Excellent	5:25	0	4:57	0	3:32	0	3:04	0	2:56	0	2:48	0
Good	6:34	1	6:02	1	4:27	1	3:55	1	3:43	1	3:31	1
Limit	9:06	3	8:24	3	6:31	3	5:49	3	5:27	2	5:06	2

5. Case Study: Progress Dynamics

Consistent practice leads to significant improvement. In one notable case (Irena K., 5th grade), after 1.5 years since mastering the multiplication table, initial diagnostic results were significantly below standard:

- **Addition:** 9m 50s (3 errors)
- **Subtraction:** 11m 05s (1 error)
- **Multiplication:** 18m 50s (17 errors)

Through a structured program (filling ~210 tables total over several months), the student achieved the following results by March:

- **Addition:** 2m 15s (0 errors)
- **Subtraction:** 2m 35s (0 errors)
- **Multiplication:** 2m 15s (0 errors)
- **Division:** 2m 00s (0 errors)

A detailed description of the results obtained from using stochastic tables in work with low-performing students can be found at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20617288>.

6. Conclusion

Good and even excellent elementary computational skills are a foundational condition for success in school mathematics. While this methodology provides the necessary base for more complex problem-solving, it remains a tool for skill development rather than a guarantee of automatic mastery of higher-level mathematical concepts.